

Collection maintenance in academic libraries: Status analysis

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Abstract

Collection maintenance is an essential practice in an academic institution. Its purpose is to maintain a well-balanced library collection that will cater to the user-centered services of the department. The academic libraries are active in collection maintenance activities, which include but are not limited to stacking, shelving, cleaning, weeding, and conservation practices. On the other hand, according to the result of this study, preservation activities have been neglected most by the participating institutions. To know the status of the mentioned activities, this paper employed the descriptive survey research design. Participants are basically chosen based on the type of library they are affiliated with. Ten (10) academic library employees were asked to answer a survey questionnaire relating to the frequency of conducting the stated collection maintenance activities. Results revealed that collection maintenance activities such as stacking, shelving, cleaning, preservation, conservation, and weeding were properly observed by the academic libraries. This activity is essential in upholding a balanced collection that meets the information needs of its user community.

Keywords: Academic libraries; Collection; Maintenance; Status.

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Introduction

A college, university, or other postsecondary educational institution's academic library is a crucial part that is run to satisfy the information and research needs of its staff, faculty, and students (Juma, 2020; Teasdale, 2023). In the Philippines, one of the professional associations for academic libraries and librarians is the Philippine Association of Academic and Research Libraries (PAARL) (Fresnido & Valerio, 2019; Ramos-Eclevia, 2023). In 2010, this association drafted a standard for academic libraries; however, the implementation of the said standard has been on hold until the present.

Collection development is the heart of the library services. It is a critical function in building the library collection, which includes selection, ordering, and acquisition. A part of collection development is collection maintenance, which is considered an integral activity due to its purpose of balancing the collection for the advantage of the community that the library serves. Collection maintenance has been integrated as a necessary part of the Collection Development Policy that is integrated usually in the Library Manual.

According to Reitz (2004), collection maintenance is any action taken on a regular basis or as required to keep the materials in a library collection in a usable state. This includes binding, rebinding, reformatting, mending, and repairing; these tasks are typically handled by the technical processing and serials department (Supangat & Salim, 2019). In the academic setting, maintenance of library resources is critical mainly because it promotes the use of diverse materials. If this practice is being overlooked, the issue of maintenance practice within the library will rise and thus affect the quality of information that it provides to the academic community. Efficiency and effectiveness of the collection are observed; thus, maintenance should include the following: stacking, shelf arrangement, cleaning, shelving, stock verification, and weeding of unwanted materials (Omehia et al., 2022). The aim of this paper is to unfold the status of the collection maintenance activities that are being observed in libraries in the academic setting—college and university.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this paper is to investigate the status of collection maintenance activities being observed in the studied academic libraries with the following specific goals:

- To ascertain the practices of academic libraries in maintaining their collection.
- To discover the status of collection maintenance in studied academic libraries.
- To determine the personnel involved in collection maintenance in academic libraries.

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey research design. According to Müller et al. (2014), asking a subgroup of people questions to collect data that may be extended to the larger target population is known as a survey. The participant population is comprised of professional and paraprofessional staff of the ten academic libraries under the study. The total number of participants is ten (10), specifically all of whom are full-time library staff in selected libraries in the Philippines. The participants were asked to answer a survey questionnaire relating to the frequency and the personnel involved in the collection maintenance activities, including stacking, shelving, cleaning, preservation, conservation, and weeding. Frequency and percentage distributions are made to determine the demonstration of library staff in the library collection maintenance activities.

Results

Discussion of the results and the presentation of data and analysis of findings were discussed in this section. It covers the identified collection maintenance practices in the academic libraries and its figured frequency of practice and the personnel responsible.

Table 1. Responsibility in collection maintenance practices in academic libraries

Practice	School Aide	Library Assistant	Librarian
Stacking		10	
Shelving		10	
Cleaning	6	4	
Preservation			5
Conservation			9
Weeding			8

Employees responsible for maintaining the collection include the librarians, the library assistants, and the school aides. In stacking the library resources, all the participants answered that it is the job of a library assistant, together with shelving. In cleaning the library area, six answered that it was done by the school aide, and four said it is the job of the library assistant. In terms of preservation, the person responsible for library preservation has a corresponding frequency of 5, and the other five respondents answered that their preservation activity is not active. Material conservation is mainly the job of a librarian, according to the nine participants, and the remaining one said that they do not practice the conservation procedure. Lastly, weeding is being observed by the eight participants, which is said to be the job of the librarians.

Table 2. Collection maintenance practice of academic libraries in terms of stacking

Practice	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Daily	5	50	1
Weekly	4	40	2
Semestral	1	10	3

The collection maintenance practice of academic libraries in terms of stacking is done daily according to the 50% of the participants, while 40% answered weekly, and 10% said they do stacking every semester. This implies that half of the participants do book stacking regularly to maintain the arrangement of shelves.

Table 3. Collection maintenance practice of academic libraries in terms of shelving

Practice	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Daily	10	100	1

The collection maintenance practice of academic libraries in terms of shelving is done daily according to all the participants. This means that they do it on a regular basis.

Table 4. Collection maintenance practice of academic libraries in terms of cleaning

Practice	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Daily	8	80	1
Weekly	2	20	2

The collection maintenance practice of academic libraries in terms of cleaning is done daily according to 80% of the participants, and 20% stated that they do it on a weekly basis. This implies that most of them are cleaning library materials regularly.

Table 5. Collection maintenance practice of academic libraries in terms of preservation

Practice	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Semestral	2	20	2.5
If Needed	2	20	2.5
Not Applicable	6	60	1

The collection maintenance practice of academic libraries in terms of preservation is not being observed according to the 60% of the participants, 30% says that their respective libraries do preservation every end of semester, and 20% answered they only do it when necessary. This means that preservation of books and other library resources must be improved to prevent degradation and outdatedness.

Table 6. Collection maintenance practice of academic libraries in terms of conservation

Practice	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Daily	1	10	3.5
Semestral	2	20	2
If Needed	6	60	1
Not Applicable	1	10	3.5

The collection maintenance practice of academic libraries in terms of conservation is done only if needed according to 60% participants, followed by every semester with corresponding 20% response. 10% has answered that their libraries do conservation in a daily basis and another 10% who answered, 'not applicable.'

This result implies that conservation of library resources can still be available for reading and other purposes when it is necessary to check whether these collections are usable or lost.

Table 7. Collection maintenance practice of academic libraries in terms of weeding

Practice	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Semestral	1	10	2.5
If Needed	8	80	1
Not Applicable	1	10	2.5

The collection maintenance practice of academic libraries in terms of weeding is not being observed according to the 50% of the participants, 30% says that their respective libraries do preservation every end of semester, and 20% answered they only do it when necessary. This result shows that half of the participants observed weeding for those with outdated versions of library resources.

Discussion

In every type of library, maintenance of materials involves continuous implementation. If not, this will threaten the usefulness and even the long-term viability of the collection. The maintenance practices that this paper focused on are as follows: stacking, shelving, cleaning, preservation, conservation, and weeding.

Shelving

The proper management of shelves is considered a necessary tool for measuring performance, satisfaction, and realization of goals that are set by the library (Khan & Batti, 2021). The circulation section is mainly involved, as users endlessly pick up nooks from the shelves, get them issued, and eventually be returned. Upon return from users, these books must be checked for damage before being shelved in their proper places. In the absence of accurate reshelving of resources, effective library operations would be difficult for clients and staff. The shelving of documents should give the users the convenience of locating the documents in an efficient manner. Shelving includes shelf reading and blocking. Shelf reading is when the library personnel ready every call number on the shelf to ensure that the books are in proper order based on the classifications being used (i.e., Dewey decimal classification, Library of Congress) (Quinn, 2024). Blocking is the process of moving each book to the end of the shelf so that all of the volumes are standing straight with book supports or book ends, and the shelf is lined up with the edge.

Stacking

Stacking is concerned with ensuring that the maximum space is being utilized and that the community of users should find the arrangement of the books convenient (Andrews et al., 2016). Although users are strictly instructed not to replace the books on the shelves, they may still do so. Books after browsing by the users are usually misplaced, and the way they are inserted is unavoidably improper, causing the papers to be torn or folded. Thus, it is essential to do shelf reading, which is beneficial in restoring the order of the arrangement and checking any damaged materials on the shelf.

Cleaning

Library materials usually get damaged by insects, dampness, heat, and dirt or dust. To avoid this, the materials must therefore be cleaned with neat and soft dusters or cloth pieces. The books and other library materials should be cleaned as often as possible, and they should be kept safe from insects, fungi, moisture, and dust (Brimblecombe et al., 2022). Materials prone to this kind of damage are those collected that are seldom being utilized by the community, as they are not being moved out of the shelves. This is usually done by the school aide assigned to maintain the cleanliness of the library facilities and resources.

Preservation and Conservation

Preservation and conservation are practices that involve prolonging the lives of library materials such as books, journals, and digital resources. All the managerial and financial factors are included in preservation. By treating and preventing degradation and destruction, it aims to preserve or restore access to papers and records (Iyishu et al., 2013). Conservation, as opposed to preservation, is the process of treating and repairing specific objects to slow down deterioration or return the materials to their usable state (McClure & Cantrell, 2013). It refers to the guidelines and procedures used to prevent loss and harm to library materials.

Weeding

To avoid having a crowded collection, libraries practice weeding. Weeding is known to be an essential activity that is intended to remove collections that are no longer useful (Nelson et al., 2020). It is the periodic or continual process of evaluating materials from the shelves, discarding those that fit the criteria for weeding permanently, or transferring them to storage. Weeding is done annually or every end of the semester during the inventory or stock verification checking.

Conclusions

The library is a user-service department in every academic institution; thus, collection access and retrieval should be of convenience. Collection maintenance is essential in upholding a balanced collection, a collection that meets the information needs of its user community. Relevant and well-maintained resources can help the community be information literate in the era of information technology. Future researchers may study the perceptions of library staff, mostly in sample sizes of at least 50-100 participants, in observing and maintaining library collections such as books, journals, and digital references.

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